

OSUN RIVER BASIN RELATIONS WITH AGRICULTURAL AND CULTURAL ACTIVITIES IN OSUN STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The importance of the Osun River Basin to the ecosystems and livelihood sustenance of people living along its course cannot be overemphasized. This assertion necessitates this study with a view to establish the relations of water bodies with agricultural and cultural activities in Osun State, Nigeria. A total of 180 respondents were selected from three LGAs in the State using a multi-stage sampling procedure and a structured questionnaire was administered during a field survey to elicit primary data from the respondents. Specifically, the study examined agricultural activities and cultural beliefs surrounding the Osun River Basin, and the perceived positive and negative effects of the River on the respondents' socioeconomic wellbeing. Data analysis was carried out using frequency and mean statistics. The study's results revealed that activities such as vegetable cultivation (78.9%), seasonal crop farming (76.7%), and marketing of agricultural produce (66.1%) were the major livelihood activities around the Osun River Basin. The River also provides sites for tourism attraction; water for domestic use, transportation and cleaning of farm structures. The study further revealed that the River Basin has significantly contributed to food security and income generation of the respondents despite the existence of cultural beliefs and rituals surrounding the use of the river. The negative impacts which threaten sustainable use of the river and surrounding ecosystems identified include; including illegal waste disposal (Mean = 2.00), flooding (Mean = 2.41), and pollution (Mean = 2.48). The study concludes that the River Basin offers extremely important ecological and economic resources that supports multiple livelihood strategies, though in the face of environmental degradation and weak management practices. It recommends environmental education, cultural integration into sustainable land-use policies which balances livelihood needs with conservation goals.

Keywords: Osun River Basin, Culture, Integration, Ecosystems, Agriculture

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INTRODUCTION

Land and water resources are foundational to agricultural and rural development, and are simultaneously inextricably connected to global challenges such as food insecurity, poverty, climate change, and the degradation and depletion of natural resources that affect the livelihoods of millions of rural people worldwide (Deng et al., 2024).

The Osun River Basin has in no small measure impacted the surrounding communities by providing direct and indirect means of livelihood, thereby contributing positively and negatively to the socioeconomic wellbeing of the people. However, Infrastructural and agricultural investments are very key to be able to achieve water resource optimization. For instance, in recent years, the Government through the Ogun-Osun River Basin Development Authority (O-ORBDA) was involved in procuring tractors and construction of dam and irrigation sites to create opportunities to scale up dry-season farming while ensuring water quality safeguards, fair water allocation and gender responsive extension services targeted at women and resource poor farmers (Bankole, 2025).

The Osun River named after the Osun deity is one of the most significant rivers in Southwestern Nigeria, it holds deep cultural, religious and agricultural importance in the region. It flows southwards through central Yoruba land in southwestern Nigeria into the Lagos Lagoon and the Atlantic Gulf of Guinea. The river is ascribed in local mythology to have been a woman who turned into flowing waters after some traumatic event though the deity is associated with fertility, love beauty and prosperity (Akinbile & Olaniran, 2020). The river provides a wide range of cultural ecosystem services such as natural scenes for eco-tourists and sites for filming Nollywood movies. Its grove situated in Osogbo holds a major cultural landscape and a UNESCO World Heritage Site recognized for its integration of culture, spirituality, art and biodiversity. Residents of communities around the river Osun rely on the river for agricultural livelihoods especially for crop irrigation (UNESCO, 2025).

The river also has enormous environmental value given its rich biodiversity. It supports plankton, wildlife resources and endangered plants. However, factors such as the cultural and traditional beliefs and different government policies affect the use of water resources and water bodies and output trend in Nigeria resulting to noticeable dwindle of agricultural activities and development in the country. Empirical evidence shows that there are systemic gaps that constrain farmers' ability to fully exploit the river's agricultural potential. Specifically, Akanbi et al. (2024) affirms that more than 60% of women vegetable farmers surveyed never received visits from extension agents. Also, Adeyemi and Ojo (2024) reported that over 70% of farmers attested to poor timeliness of broadcasts during crucial planting periods. Diminishing soil fertility; poor water quantity and quality for crop irrigation and domestic use; erosion and sedimentation often have all been attributed to deforestation, unregulated expansion, and poor waste management (Oyeleye, 2025). According to UNESCO (2025), opportunities for participatory management approaches that respect traditional values and promote sustainable livelihoods are presented by the coexistence of sacred and

productive landscapes. The increase in population growth and the challenges of attaining food security necessitate the need to harness all available resources and develop management strategies crucial to improving water use for optimal agricultural production. This study was therefore carried out to examine the agricultural activities and cultural beliefs surrounding the Osun River Basin, and the perceived positive and negative effects of the River on the respondents' socioeconomic wellbeing. The study will also generate information that will help in the development of the nation's water resources and the cultural heritage. It stands to provide insights to new potentials and opportunities at achieving food security, alternative livelihoods and means of increasing revenue for the farmers while ensuring the agricultural development.

METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out in Osun State Nigeria which is a state in South-Western Nigeria; bounded to the east by Ekiti and Ondo States, to the north by Kwara State, to the south by Ogun State and to the west by Oyo State. The state is named for the River Osun, a vital river which flows through the state. The state practices mainly agriculture along with artisanal mining and livestock herding. The study's population were farmers in Osun State. Three Local Government Areas were purposively selected from the senatorial district of Osun State namely; Osogbo, Ede North and Boripe Local Government Areas because the river Osun takes its path through these Local Government Areas. In the second stage, two communities located along the River basin where agricultural and tourism activities were prominent were purposively selected in the three Local Government Areas namely Ire, Iragbiji, Isale Osun, Oja Oba, Olodo/Gaa Fulani, and Owode Ede. In each of these communities, 30 respondents were randomly selected to make a total of 180 respondents for the study. The study made use of primary data which was collected with the aid of pretested structured questionnaire initially administered outside of the study area. The structured questionnaire was thereafter administered during a field survey after correlation were confirmed statistically significant. The questionnaire sourced information on agricultural activities practiced around the river, the impacts of the river on the socioeconomic wellbeing of residents and the Cultural Activities and Belief Surrounding the Use of the River. The former was determined on a Likert scale of very severe, severe, mildly severe and Not at all severe. Data were analysed using means, frequencies and percentages. The latter was determined by presenting a list to which the respondents answered yes or no.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Agricultural Activities Practiced around Osun River Basin

As shown in Figure 1, vegetable cultivation (78.9%) and cultivation of seasonal crops such as maize, yam, cassava, and rice (76.7%) represent the most prevalent agricultural practices. These high percentages suggest that land-based arable farming remains the primary livelihood activity in the area. Vegetable farming is very popular near wetlands and riverbanks because of the availability of residual soil moisture, as also confirmed by Ajibefun et al. (2022) in their study on lowland vegetable production in Ondo and

Ekiti States. Agricultural produce marketing was also relatively high (66.1%). This points to the fact that there is an appreciable production systems that is market oriented with the incorporation of peri-urban and local value chains.

The practiced agricultural activities in the moderate category included; planting of trees for timber purposes (43.3%), cultivation of forage/pastures and fish farming (35.0%). This is a likely reflection of integrated farming and environmental protection practices among the respondents. This implies an emergence of agro-ecological integration, though with a little widespread. Ogunbameru and Ejigu (2021) affirmed that agroforestry practices have been gaining acceptance as a strategy for income diversification and land management practice in the Southwestern Nigeria.

The adoption of the practices is however often limited by constraints of land tenure and low awareness of long-term benefits. The fish farming appearing in the moderate category beats the apriori expectation that respondents will take the advantage of the availability of water to boost their fishing activities. This may be occasioned by the cultural taboos surrounding the Osun River, inadequate capital, high cost of acquiring fishing inputs and the technicalities associated with aquaculture. This finding is supported by Gomma (2020), who affirmed a potential reduction in returns and investment in improved fish production as a result of high cost of fishing inputs.

Fish processing (30.0%) and fish marketing (28.3%) have low participation in relation to other agricultural activities in the study area. Iyiola and Jenyo-Oni (2023) also discovered that fishing production along the Osun River Basin was affected by environmental pressures. This finding is further supported by Akinbile and Olorunfemi (2024) who confirmed that due to traditional restrictions on water body and poor extension support, there is modest participation of smallholder farmers in aquaculture despite the abundant water resources in Nigeria. The low participation in fishing enterprises indicates the inability to maximize opportunity for expansion of the blue-economy, particularly that of aquaculture and irrigation development. The study reveals that land-based farming was the most prominent agricultural activities around the Osun River Basin. The aquatic based enterprises, though permissible, were less practiced as a results of cultural, technical and economic constraints. This reinforces the need for integration of cultural value into agricultural development with the emphasis on sustainable use of both water and land resources.

Figure 1: Practiced Agricultural activities around Osun River Bain (Multiple Responses)

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Cultural Activities and Beliefs Surrounding the Use of Osun River Basin

The respondents' customs and traditional belief relating to water bodies are deeply rooted in their culture. According to the results in Table 1, 86.1% indicated that there are customs and values peculiar to water bodies which reflect their significance in daily life existence. The key emphasis of water bodies in cultural identity formation is seen with a majority (72.2%) acknowledging the conduct of rituals and ceremonies around water bodies, (61.1%) believed on the influence of water in shaping destinies and local identities. Also, many (62.2%) believed that water bodies have influence in determining the weather and climatic conditions, not leaving the global climate change concerns out of cultural context. About 60.0% believed there are taboos surrounding the use of water body, which was confirmed in the permissible agricultural activities around the water body with fish farming having a low participation. Similarly, gender and caste were revealed to be among cultural issues related to water bodies with cases of 58.3% and 53.9% of gender beliefs and practices associated with the use of the water and restrictions on the use of the river for certain groups respectively. About 54.4% attributed that there are traditional healing practices associated with the river, signifying the spiritual connotation of culture and water. However, only 35.6% agreed that there are measures put in place to revive traditional practices, with 21.1% acknowledging that there are indigenous conservation practices related to the water body. This decline points out the risk of losing indigenous cultural practices connected to water bodies. This may be due to modernization, urbanization, neglect in community based conservation ethics and decline in the effectiveness of traditional authority structures.

Though the study results established the existence remarkable cultural traditions and belief that are water related, they are also pointers to the gradual decline in cultural preservation and indigenous practices that are necessary for water resource management. There is a need to develop extension models that integrates cultural heritage into ecosystems in planning agricultural development along the River Osun Basin.

Table 1: Cultural Activities and Belief Surrounding the Use of the River

Cultural Activities and Beliefs	Freq.	%
Customs and values related to the water body	155	86.1
Rituals and ceremonies conducted near the water body	130	72.2
Traditional belief on weather conditions associated with the water	112	62.2
Presence of traditional story tellers and legends surrounding the river	110	61.1
Influence of the water in shaping destinies and local identities	110	61.1
Taboos surrounding the water	108	60.0
Gender beliefs and practices associated with the use of the water	105	58.3
Traditional belief about crop yield and general agricultural productivity	102	56.7
Traditional festivals connected to the river	102	56.7
Traditional healing practices associated with the river	98	54.4
Restrictions on the use of the river for certain groups	97	53.9
Traditions associated with any form of use of the water at the site	84	46.7
Measures set to revive traditional practices	64	35.6
Indigenous conservation practices related to the water body	38	21.1
Membership of cultural groups to be able to participate in activities around the water body	35	19.4

Source: Field Survey 2025

Perceived Positive and Negative Effects of the River Osun on the Respondents' Socioeconomic Wellbeing

Table 2 shows that the river provides support for all-round agricultural cultivation (Mean = 1.58) and irrigation farming (Mean = 1.97) which is very essential for increased crop production. There is a boost in crop yield from the availability of residual soil moisture and improved soil health by rivers and floodplains in Southwest, Nigeria especially during the dry season (Ayanlade & Jegede, 2022). The River Basin also provided water for domestic use (Mean = 1.64). This result aligns with Olanrewaju *et al.* (2023), who reported that the Osun River Basin serves as source of water for livestock management; and household cooking and washing. Other major positive effects of the river included; means of transportation (Mean = 1.68), farm structures cleaning (Mean = 1.87) and provision of habitat for aquatic creatures (Mean = 2.01). Furthermore, the river provides source of water for hydropower generation on a small scale (Mean = 2.14) and alternative source of water during dry spells (Mean = 2.17). These multifaceted roles of the water

underscore its importance in strengthening the local economies and overall quality of life. In addition to the agricultural and energy resilience, the leading effect of the river on the socio-economic wellbeing of respondent is the income generated through tourism (Mean = 2.76). Ojo et al. (2022) and UNESCO (2021) affirm that the Osun-Osogbo Sacred grove enhances income generation through tourism activities. The study findings imply that both ecologically and economically, the River Osun Basin has diverse positive effects which included; agricultural livelihood activities, hydropower and tourism support.

Despite these numerous positive effects of the River Basin on the socioeconomic wellbeing of the respondents, some negative effects were identified with the river. The most critical of them was water pollution (Mean =2.48), which only exacerbated climate change concerns. Other negative effects include; habitat for dangerous aquatic animals (Mean =2.43), flooding of farmland (Mean =2.41), hideouts for insurgency (Mean =2.01) and illegal waste disposal (Mean =2.0). The negative effects all have mean values above 2.0 which implies a relatively high effect with a grand mean score of 2.34. These results reveal the risk of loss of farm land or a possible decline in agricultural activities due to insecurity challenges, inaccessibility or other environmental factors. The Nigerian river systems are threatened by environmental and public health mostly caused by agricultural runoff, household wastes and industrial effluents (Olaniyan et al., 2024; FAO, 2012). Also, Adeyemo and Ogundele (2023) confirmed that flooding patterns have increased around riverbanks as a result of climate variability and deforestation.

Table 2: Perceived Effects of the River Osun Basin on the Socioeconomic Wellbeing of the Respondents

Impacts	Mean
Positive Effects	
Generation of income through tourism	2.76
Water source during dry spell	2.17
Small scale hydropower generation	2.14
Habitat for aquatic animals	2.01
Water for Irrigation and all-year round agriculture	1.97
Farm structures cleaning	1.87
Means of transportation	1.68
Source of water for domestic use	1.64
Increase in crop yield	1.58
Water resources conservation	1.40
Grand Mean for Positive Effects	1.92
Negative Effects	
Water pollution	2.48
Habitat for dangerous aquatic creatures	2.43
Flooding of farmland	2.41
Hideouts for insurgency	2.01
Illegal waste disposal	2.00
Grand Mean for Negative Effects	2.34

Source: Field Survey, 2023

CONCLUSION

The Osun River Basin contributes immensely in shaping the livelihood of the people along its course through their involvement in diverse agricultural and tourism activities. The river enhances agricultural productivity by provision of water sources for aquaculture, irrigation, particularly in the cultivation of seasonal crops and vegetables. In addition to the agricultural importance of the river, the study also affirms the existence of water related traditions and beliefs which are deeply rooted in the people's culture though there was a decline in the practice of resource management that respect indigenous knowledge systems. The study established an imbalance in the perceived positive and negative effects of the river basin which if not addressed poses insecurity challenges, possible loss of farm land and decline in agricultural and economic productivity. In essence, given the potentials of the Osun River Basin to sustain livelihoods, it also portends environmental and inaccessibility risks when regulatory measures and water resources management approaches that culture are not practiced.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The relevant authorities in the management of the Osun River basin such as the Osun State Ministry of Environment and the Ogun-Osun River Basin Development Authority (O-ORBDA) should jointly implement strategies that can effectively manage activities along the river course to control flood and pollution while at the same time maximize the agricultural use of the River. It is however important that in order to ensure sustainable management practices around the River, local authorities should be involved from planning to implementation of strategies or models to be used in order to incorporate indigenous knowledge systems and cultural values to the practices.

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